

The Molecular Dynamics Simulation of Interactions in Shock-Compressed Systems

V.S. Znamenski

Kabardino-Balkarian State University

P.O.Box 90, Nalchik-04, KBR

360004, Russia

P.F. Zilberman and I.N. Pavlenko

Kabardino-Balkarian State Agriculture Academy, Nalchik, KBR, 360004, Russia

Abstract

A general study of some atomic aspects of the shock and unload phenomena is presented. Computer molecular-dynamics simulations based on the Born-Maier-Huggins' and Poling's potential models have been used to study the shock-compression phenomena.

1. Introduction

This work is an extending development of our investigations on molecular dynamics simulation of contact melting [1-12]. Contact melting is a phenomenon of lowering of melting point at the contiguity zone of the two different crystals. Our molecular dynamics simulations showed that system of two contact bodies has the new physical properties. It happens when only masses and sizes of particles are difference in the difference sides of the boundary. And we are interested in the question: What will as a result of differences of other system parameters, as desksides of location of particles, group average velocities, and so on, on sides of the section border of two materials forming the contact? Thus we started the studies of shock compressed systems [13].

The research on shock - compressed conditions is closely connected with work on production of amorphous materials, welding by explosion, making the artificial diamonds, and with other similar works. Molecular dynamics simulations have been broadly used to study microscopic features of substances. From the simulation, the time dependence of positions and velocities of particles are obtained by numerically integrating the equation of motion. Therefore, the MD

method has been used to simulate a nonequilibrium phenomena. The MD method has been used to simulate crystallisation, glass formation [14] and melting processes for many systems [15-16].

Our studies were conducted for the ionic system. The alkali halides have been the preferred model system. Their physical and chemical properties have been widely investigated, and are well understood. There is a considerable interest in the understanding of phenomena by extreme conditions, for example, pressure-induced solid-solid phase transition [17].

2. Some shock compression physical phenomena

The feature of processes, which take place by the shock compression, is a structural modification of surface layers with practically absence of diffusion. In the Fig.1-2 you can see some simplified scheme of receiving of two aspects of shock compression phenomena. The welding by explosion is shown in Fig. 1. The cumulative effect is shown in Fig. 2. The beginnings of these processes are alike. Initial location and velocity of surfaces are shown in Fig 3. Some combinations of the velocity V and the angle α lead to a welding or a cumulation. The cumulative effect occurs when surfaces have a specific angle. Shock - compression conditions in the region of the collision of two surfaces gives these effects. It is known that welding by explosion can connect two substances, which can not be connected by other ways. The importance of technical significance has a phenomenon of strengthening by explosion shown in Fig 4.

3. MD simulation of the cumulative effect

The use of simulation on atomic scale is the possibly best means to finding - out for formation mechanisms under actions of shock loads and for revealing of processes, which take place thus. The molecular dynamic method (MD) allows to trace the movement of atoms or ions under the action of interparticle forces, and also to research the modification of its structures under actions of shock loads.

We made the simulation for ionic crystals with the BHM potential for various initial speeds. The estimate of structure characteristics was implemented by calculation of radial distribution functions (RDF) and by visualisation of particle trajectories. We note that the RDF does not allow us to find the great variety of structures, which are formed. Therefore it is possible to receive the maximal information only by visualisation of particle trajectories. We made the

average of particle co-ordinates for the time of average in fluctuation period to the exception of influence of thermal fluctuations on visualisation. The MD-experiments had shown the existence of strong processes of the structural rebuilding and the transfer to the amorphous structure under shock interaction in the surface zone of several crystal layers. There are observed the cumulative effects on atomic scale of size. In Fig. 5 you can see the first simplified scheme of molecular dynamic experiment to study the shock - compression phenomena as the welding by explosion and the cumulative effect. The initial coordinates and velocities were randomly varied to provide the best fit to the expected effect.

4. Discussion

In our simulation we have recently discovered that sometimes certain ions move with more increased velocity and more linearly can take a long time. It happens by random configuration of particles. We would like to draw your attention to a question one can raise: Do the observed properties truly exist, or are they simply artifacts of numerical divergence? We specially examined situations, when the calculation system has artifacts of numerical divergence. It may be for example, when the starting position of two particles are at a very short, unrealistic distance. The system behaviour is absolutely different in this case. We think that the received property is true. We are studying the problem.

We can say that there is the same computer evidence for a jet-commutation effect on the scale of a hundred particles. With our small number of computer experiments, it does not seem reasonable to draw any definite conclusions as the mechanism of commutation. Our statistics are not rich enough to give conclusive results. Under the microscopic shock compression lattice becomes excited. We presuppose the stochastic shock influences are the ordinary events on normal conditions. The external shock action considerably increases the number of internal overshock events. These overshock have stronger specific power. They are the basic reason for phenomena such as welding by explosion and hardening by explosion. Atomic implication of this process is destruction of old structures and formation of new stable nodes. We should add, however, that MD simulation is very computer time consuming and our simulation result should be considered preliminary and our statistics are not rich enough to give the accurate confirmation of our ideas.

5. MD simulation of substance properties in the shock or unloading wave

A different way to study the shock-compression is the simulation of a substance in (a) the significant increasing or (b) the decreasing of interatomic space. It is the simulation of substance properties (a) in the shock-wave or (b) in the unloading-wave. Modelling of shock compression was realised by the changing of the size of the calculation box. For simulation of these effects we use the same models. The first model started the calculation of the ion movements from nodes of the cubical net. Temperature has a broad range of values. First, we have constructed the initial coordinate and velocity of ions. Then by using the numerical methods of temperature stabilisation we have made the run of MD simulations with different temperatures and values of size of cubic cell. One initial structure of the particle system is a regular cubic lattice of ions as for *NaCl*, and casual velocities. Second initial structure is some result of preceding MD simulations. The states of system have been examined by use of the mean square displacement $R^2_k(t)$ of ions

$$R^2_k(t) = \langle r_i(t) - r_i(t_0) \rangle^2_{>k} \quad (1)$$

where $r_i(t)$ is the position vector of the i -th ion at time t , $\langle \rangle$ denoted the average, k denoted the type of ions.

We have developed a computer program, which can be used for simulation of many-bodies problems for classical systems with central interactions between particles, and can get an evolution in time for ensembles of particles. The ensemble consists of 4 ion species, described by the corresponding ion positions and velocities. The program allows one to get the mean-square displacements of ions, diffusion coefficients, partial radial distribution functions, normalised velocity autocorrelation functions and other data. Simulation was realised on traditional MD schemes using the BHM [18] and Pauling's potentials. The number of all ions is 216, and the numbers of each type of ions are 64. Molecular Dynamics Simulation 54 A^+ , 54 B^- , 54 C^+ , and 54 D^- were placed in the periodic cube. Our cubic simulation cell is divided initially by two equal parts corresponding to the AB and CD species respectively. The time step was 7-10 fs. At the initial stage of the MD simulation, the NTV ensemble was settled. The data analyses were done with the final 1000 steps. The general statements of numerical experiments are given in table 1.

The ***AB-CD*** notation denotes the following: chemical system ***AB*** is initially located in the first half of a cubic cell and system ***BC*** is initially located in the second half. The ***A⁺, B⁻, C⁺, D⁻*** compound denotes an homogeneous ion mixture.

TABLE 1. The general statements of numerical experiments

System composition	Initial configuration of ions	Some details or/and purpose of experiment
<i>NaCl-KBr</i>	regular ideal cubic lattice	an effect of the ion exchange: <i>Cl⁻</i> and <i>Br⁻</i>
<i>Na⁺, Br⁻, K⁺, Cl⁻</i>	amorphous state	
<i>NaBr-KCl</i>	regular ideal cubic lattice	
<i>NaBr-KCl</i>	regular ideal cubic lattice	locations of <i>Br⁻</i> and <i>Cl⁻</i> are fixed
<i>Na⁺, Br⁻, K⁺, Cl⁻</i>	amorphous state	locations of <i>Br⁻</i> and <i>Cl⁻</i> are fixed

The diffusion coefficients D_k ($k = 1, 2, 3, 4$) have been estimated by using the evolution parameters of a system and have been calculated by means of the relation

$$\langle \{r_i(t) - r_i(t_0)\}^2 \rangle_k = 6 D_k t + C_k, t_0 < t < T, \quad (2)$$

The velocity autocorrelation function is defined as,

$$Z_k(t) = \langle V_i(0) V_i(t) \rangle_k / \langle V_i^2 \rangle_k \quad (3)$$

where V_i is the velocity of ions, and k is a number of the ion type.

We have used here two potential approximations by Pauling [7] and Fumi-Tosi. The Pauling's potential between ions labelled " i " and " j " is given by

$$V_{ij}(r) = e^2 / (4\pi\epsilon_0 r) (q_i q_j r^{-1} + [(s_i + s_j)/r]^p / (p + 1)) \quad (4)$$

where s are parameters, $p = 8$ (the hardness parameter), ϵ_0 is the electric constant, $q \cdot e$ are the ionic charges, e is the electron charge. The Fumi-Tosi potential is of the form

$$V_{ij}(r) = Z_i Z_j e^2 / (4 \pi \epsilon_0 r) + (1 + Z_i/n_i + Z_j/n_j) b \exp[(\sigma_i + \sigma_j - r)/\rho] - C_{ij}/r^6 - D_{ij}/r^8 \quad (5),$$

here Z is an ionic charge number, n the number of the electrons in an outer shell, b a repulsion parameter, σ a value characteristic of an ion size and ρ a softness parameter.

6. Results

We run a number of experiments consecutively varying sizes of cell and temperature, calculating diffusion coefficients. The beginning of sharp increasing the diffusion coefficients identifies the melting point. Here with sharp increases the diffusion coefficient is observed simultaneously for all types of ions, the difference is concluded at values of diffusion coefficient only. On the fig. 6 two areas of the phase diagram "solid-liquid" well stand out. Comparison of received results for systems *NaCl-KBr* and *NaBr-KCl* has shown that for these systems phase diagrams "solid-liquid" are alike. If different systems are constituted of alike ions, temperatures of transition "solid-liquid" are alike for these systems for given sizes of cells. However, values of diffusion coefficients of ions are different in the fluid phase. For instance diffusion coefficients

of sodion in *NaCl-KBr* are smaller than in *NaBr-KCl*. Reduction of cell length of calculated cube from 2700 prior to 2550 pm brings about the raising of a melting point from 800 prior to 1500 K for *NaCl-KBr* system. Changing a pressure from 0 prior to 5 GPa corresponds to changing a melting point. Another result is observed for the unordered mixture. The Amorphous state of such a system is unchangeable when changing the size of a cell (for a given time of the experiment). Comparison shows that for the amorphous system the diffusion coefficients are vastly more high when the accounting cell has the small sizes (Fig.7). Diffusion coefficient values for amorphous and regular systems become alike when increasing the sizes of cell prior to such, which are characteristic of the liquid state of the originally regular system.

We looked for system factors that act on the ions diffusion. For instance we stopped some ions, assigning to them very great masses, to estimate how they act on the diffusion of one ions and moving other ions. When we had a freeze of all negative ions, the positive ions noticeably did not change their own diffusion coefficient values. It was characteristic for all system states.

Analysis of radial distribution functions has shown the following: Increasing a temperature of experiment brings about reducing the nearest distance between ions, which is reached due to heat moving of the ions for the originally ranked system. An interesting dependency is found at variation of cell sizes. Increasing the sizes of cells first brings about the growing of this feature, then to its reduction. For instance the least *Na - Br* distance increases from 2.7 prior to 2.9 Å but then again decreases prior to 2.7. Such behaviour is explained by the phase transition "solid-liquid". In the solid phase an increasing of the average distance between ions is accompanied by the increasing of the minimum attainable distance. In the liquid phase a free volume increases by the cell size increasing, but the nearest ions again have a closer minimum distance to one another. Another result is observed for the unordered mixture of ions, which simulate the amorphous state: The initial increasing of the minimum distance between ions then changes onto the constancy. Similar dependencies are received for positions of first maximums of radial distribution functions, characterising average distances between nearby ions.

We have shown that MD method gives some reasonably reliable way to determine the microscopic characteristics of material at the shock compression phenomena. The simulation has shown that for the temperature of experiment ($T = 700-1500$ K), and for a time of the experiment ($t = 1$ ps) originally crystalline structure can be changed and formed an amorphous or liquid

state. The changing of the temperature and the cell size is accompanied by the changing of the time of the system transition into the amorphous state. Crystalline lattice is more stable under strain stresses at the wave of unload, spraining together with the system. The growth of free volumes quickly becomes a main mechanism of expansion of amorphous structure.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the Russian Foundation of Basic Research under Grant No. 95-01-01567. The financial support of the Scientific Affairs Division of NATO is gratefully acknowledged.

Figure 1. The welding by explosion. Figure 2. The cumulative effect

Figure 3. The initial configuration and movement for the cumulative effect and welding by explosion.

Figure 4. The phenomenon of the strengthening by explosion.

Figure 5. The scheme of molecular dynamic experiment to study shock - compression. V is the group velocity. V_i is some velocity of ion or atom. V_{it} is the thermal velocity. $V_i = V_{it} + V$

Figure 6. The self-diffusion coefficients D of Na^+ ions vs. T and edge length of a cubic cell calculated for the $NaBr-KCl$ system.

Figure 7. The same as in Fig. 6 for the amorphous system.

References

1. Savintsev, P.A., Znamenski, V.S., Zilberman, P.F. et al. (1995) Nanophysics of contact melting: simulation by molecular dynamics method, Bulletin of Kabardino-Balkarian State University, Series: Physics and Mathematics Sciences 1, 273-242.
2. Goncharenko, E.A., Znamenskii, V.S., Zilberman, P.F. et al. (1995) The molecular-dynamics simulation of influence of external electromagnetic fields on contact melting of ionic crystals, The Physics and Chemistry of Material Processing (Russian) 3, 94-99.

3. Znamenskii, V.S., Zilberman, P.F., Goncharenko, E.A. et al. (1995) The research by molecular-dynamics method into the contact melting and structure-dynamic properties of NaCl-RbCl system, Zhurnal Fizicheskoi Khimii 5, 845-848.
4. Znamenski, V.S. (1994) The statistical simulation of contact melting, Nonlinear Boundary-value Problems of Mathematical Physics and Their Applications. Collection of scientific works. Kiev. Mathematical Institute, 81-82.
5. Znamenskii, V.S. et al. (1995) Parameters of contact melting in ionic systems: molecular dynamics simulations with Pauling and Fumi-Tosi potentials, Inorganic Materials 4, 483-485.
6. Znamenski, V.S. et al. (1993) Investigation of contact melting by methods of molecular dynamics, Zhurnal fizicheskoi khimii 7, 1504-1507.
7. Znamenskii, V.S. Savincev, P.A., and Zil'berman, P.F. (1993) Molecular dynamics study of the contact melting - Method. Russ. J. Phys. Chem. 7, 1349-1352.
8. Znamenski, V.S. et al. (1995) The some aspects of contact-melting research by molecular dynamics methods, The Russian Conference "The Physics of interphasic phenomena and interaction processes of energy streams with solids", Terscol, Russia. 3-6 October 1995, Thesis of Reports, Nalchik, K-BSU, 60-62.
9. Znamenski, V.S., Zilberman P.F. (1995) The problems of analysis of space configurations of particles, which is received at computer molecular-dynamics experiment, International Technological Seminar "Problems of Transmissions and Processing of Information in Information Networks", Moscow, Thesis of Reports, Scientific and Information Centre of Problems of Intelligent Property, 50-52.
10. Znamenski, V.S., Zilberman, P.F., Gelfand, T.V. at al. (1995) Computing techniques in physics of contact melting phenomenon, 10th Summer School GPS EPS on Computing Techniques in Physics "High Performance Computing in Science". Abstracts. Scalsky Dvur, Czech Republic. 5-14 September.
11. Znamensky, V.S. et al. (1994) Molecular dynamics simulation of the ionic crystals contact melting, Proceedings of the 6-th Joint EPS - APS International conference on physics computing. Lugano, Switzerland. 22-26 August, 645-647.

12. Savintsev, P.A., Zil'berman, P.F., Znamenski, V.S. (1990) Molecular dynamics method in personal computer for analysis of contact melting for ionic crystals, Structures and properties for metal and slag melts. Scient. rep. of the VII All-Union conf. Cheliabinsk, USSR, 1,II, 207-208.
13. Znamenski, V.S., Zilberman, P.F. (1995) Numerical simulation of the surface-blow amorphization in explosive welding by the molecular dynamics method, Russian Seminar "Structural Heredity in Processes of Super-Rapid Hardening of Melts", Izhevsk, 26-28 September, 1995, Theses of Reports, 121-122.
14. Watanabe, M.S. and Tsumuraya, K. (1987) Crystallisation and glass formation processes in liquid sodium: A molecular dynamics study, J. Chem.Phys. 8, 4891-4900.
15. Fincham, D (1994) Dynamic simulation of molecular and ionic materials, J.Mol.Graphics 12 , 29-32.
16. Angel 1, C.A., Scamehorn, C.A., Phifer, C.C. at al. (1988) Ion Dynamics Studies of Liquid and Glassy Silicates, and Gas-in-Liquid Solutions, Phys Chem Minerals 15 , 221-227.
17. Martin Pendas, A., Luana, V., Recio, J.M. et al. (1994) Pressure-induced B1-B2 phase transition in alkali halides: General aspects from first-principles calculations, Physical Review B 5, 3066-3074.
18. Sangster, M.J.L. and Dixon, M. (1976) Interionic Potentials and their Use in Simulations of the Molten Salts, Advanced in Physics 3 , 247-342.

Computer Modelling of
Electronic and
Atomic Processes
in Solids

Edited by
Roderick C. Tennyson and Arnold E. Kiv

NATO ASI Series

3, High Technology - 96, 22

Cite:

Znamenski V.S., Zilberman P.F., Pavlenko I.N. The Molecular Dynamics Simulation of Interactions in Shock-Compressed Systems // Computer Modelling of Electronic and Atomic Processes in Solids , Ed. R.Tennyson, A.E.Kiv; NATO ASI Series, Kluwer Publishers, Amsterdam, 1997. P. 149-157.

<https://link.springer.com/book/9789401063876>

About this book

This publication presents the proceedings of the NATO Advanced Research Workshop (ARW) on Computer Modelling of Electronic and Atomic Processes in Solids. This ARW was held at Szklarska Poreba, Wroclaw, Poland from May 20 -23, 1996, and brought together scientists from Canada, England, Germany, Israel, Latvia, Poland, Russia, Switzerland, United States, Ukraine and Uzbekistan. The NATO Advanced

Research Workshops program is designed to increase collaboration and exchange of knowledge between the Eastern and Western scientific communities. This particular NATO ARW has already succeeded in that effort, and has spawned collaboration agreements and programs. One joint project in space materials has led to the launch of an experiment to the Russian MIR space station. This NATO ARW was also fortunate to be held concurrently with a workshop of the Wroclaw Technical University, in the same location, which focused on glass materials, thus providing for a larger scientific audience for a number of presentations of both groups. The primary emphasis of this ARW was on computer models, ranging from fundamental atomic, molecular and electronic structures and processes, through to macroscopic descriptions of materials in terms of their structure and properties. Various elements discussed in these proceedings include environmental effects, predictions of properties, correlations with experiments and material performance parameters. Applications to space and electronics were emphasized.

This Document:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1sXl-AbH1J6nZ9EylcD4_NJHhzwts3RSfJhtveJAINBQ/edit?usp=sharing

https://docs.google.com/document/d/e/2PACX-1vRJg27EA7nQMYnKgu7xWpGOQFlkcoRupONmtJ2nMC_pRgFSHatTDTUh5zM0eBFu1L9VCs0XBQm4aBPL/pub